

Potentiometric Study of the Oxidation of Sulphite by Alkaline Permanganate

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The reaction of KMnO_4 with sulphite in alkaline media has been followed potentiometrically using platinum and gold electrodes. The reaction is quantitative and analytically significant under the conditions of investigations. Mn(IV) is the sole product of reduction.

From the redox curves some formal potential (E°) values for Mn(VII)/Mn(IV) couple have been computed.

A SURVEY of literature reveals that earlier workers¹⁻¹⁴ have considered the quantitative estimation of sulphite by permanganate to be impracticable.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Details of investigations have been described in the earlier paper of this series (*this journal*).

TABLE 1

Cell : 5 ml of 0.025M Na_2SO_3 solution.
Titrant : 0.01662M KMnO_4 solution.
Medium : Sodium hydroxide (Nitrogen atmosphere).

Concentration of alkali	Temp., °C/ Periods of storage (hr)	Inflexions in ml of oxidant	Moles of oxidant per mole of reductant
N/80	RT/24	4.8	0.6385
	RT/72	4.9	0.6520
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	0.6650
N/10	RT/24	4.8	0.6385
	RT/72	4.9	0.6520
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	0.6650
N	RT/24	4.8	0.6385
	RT/72	4.9	0.6520
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	0.6650
2N	RT/24	4.8	0.6285
	RT/72	4.9	0.6520
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	0.6650

RT = Room temperature (25°)

TABLE 2

Cell : 5 ml of 0.01662M KMnO_4 solution.
Titrant : 0.025M Na_2SO_3 solution.
Medium : Sodium hydroxide (Nitrogen atmosphere)

Concentration of alkali	Temp., °C/ Periods of storage (hr)	Inflexions in ml of reductant	Moles of reductant per mole of oxidant
N/80	RT/24	5.2	1.44
	RT/72	5.1	1.48
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.50
N/10	RT/24	5.2	1.44
	RT/72	5.1	1.48
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.50
N	RT/24	5.2	1.44
	RT/72	5.1	1.48
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.50
2N	RT/24	5.2	1.44
	RT/72	5.1	1.48
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.50

RT = Room temperature (25°)

TABLE 3—FORMAL POTENTIALS (E°) OF $\text{MnO}_4^-/\text{MnO}_2$ SYSTEM IN NaOH MEDIA

E° (volts) ¹⁵	Alkali concentration	E° (volts)	
		Pt electrode	Au electrode
0.588 with Pt electrode	2N	0.7332	0.7278
	N	0.7321	0.7277
	N/10	0.7225	0.7195
	N/80	0.7177	0.7140

These values of formal potentials (E°) have been calculated from the observed values of e.m.f. during the progress of the titrations using the well known Nernst's relations. Since E° , to which Swift¹⁶ refers as the practical standard potential, includes the activity coefficient ratios of the ions involved, the values of the concentrations of oxidised and reduced species involved were calculated in terms

of a single variable, i.e. the amounts of titrants added at regular intervals. The values that occur in the table are the means of several values calculated.

Results and Discussion

The tables and the figure present a summary of the experimental results and the type of redox curve

obtained respectively. A single very sharp inflexion occurs at 2/3 mole of permanganate per mole of sulphite whether the former is gradually added to the latter, or *vice versa*, in all concentrations of alkali used. This corresponds to the following stoichiometric equation :

Such a quantitative reaction, however, occurs only when the reaction mixtures are stored for 6 hr at 70° or for 120 hr at the room temperature (25°). There is no evidence of the formation of Mn or S species of intermediate oxidation states and the

reaction may be taken to be of considerable analytical significance.

The potential changes recorded by the two electrodes (Pt and Au) run nearly parallel, though the values are not identical. The Pt electrode, however, proved to be superior both in regard to reversibility and to potential jump at the equivalence point.

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AA' : Na_2SO_3 soln. in cell,
 BB' : KMnO_4 soln. in cell.
 Medium : (N)NaOH
 O : readings with Pt electrode,
 X : readings with Au electrode.